

Why The UN And the World Failed to Control the Israel–Palestine War Conflict, And Is the Two–State Formula an Ultimate Solution?

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ABSTRACT:

A lasting end to the Israeli–Palestinian conflict can only come through a two–State solution. one that starts with Palestinian freedom and leads to shared peace and security in the region, or one that continues denying this freedom and dooms the region to endless conflict. “Israel should no longer entertain the illusion that there is somehow a third path whereby it can choose continued occupation and colonialism and apartheid and somehow still achieve regional peace and security.” The cease–fire and a renewed vision of a two–State solution are critical for preventing the proliferation of extremism and extremist ideologies, urging to start preparing an international peace conference “to address all the puzzle pieces of a two–State solution in a comprehensive manner”.

KEYWORDS:

United Nations, World, Israel, Palestine, Jerusalem, Gaza Strip.

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In the past century, a multitude of local and international actors has been involved in the shaping of the Israeli–Palestinian conflict. War conflict is driven by several factors. Such as ethnic, national, historical, and religious. Israel, the subsequent escalation of oppression and violence against Palestinians, resistance against settler colonialism, and different actors that played a role over the last century. Conflict occurred in British–ruled Palestine between Arabs and Jews who migrated to the area, seeking a national home as they fled persecution in Europe and citing biblical ties the land. In 1947, the United Nations agreed a plan partitioning Palestine into Arab and Jewish states with International rule over Jerusalem. Jewish leaders accepted the plan, which gave them 56% of the land. The Arab League rejected it. The state of Israel was declared on May 14, 1948. A day later, five Arab states attacked. The war ended with Israel controlling 77% of the territory. Some 700, 00 Palestinians fled or were driven from their homes, ending up in Jordan, Lebanon and Syria as well as

in the Gaza Strip, the West Bank and East Jerusalem. In a 1967 war, Israel captured the West Bank, including East Jerusalem, from Jordan and Gaza from Egypt. The Palestinians remain stateless, with most living under Israeli occupation. Some mostly descendants of Palestinians who remained in Israel after its creation have Israeli citizenship.

What was Israel before 1948 and how was it created?

Source: <https://www.auphr.org/index.php/resources/map-card>

Britain took control of the area known as Palestine in World War one, following the defeat of the Ottoman Empire, which had ruled that part of the Middle East. An Arab majority and a Jewish minority lived there, as well as other ethnic groups. Tensions between the Jewish and Arab populations deepened when the UK agreed in principle to the establishment of a “national home” in Palestine for Jewish people a pledge known as the Balfour Declaration. Jews had historical links to the land, but Palestinian Arabs also had a claim dating back centuries and opposed the move. The British said the rights of Palestinian Arabs already living there had to be protected. Between the 1920s and 1940s, the number of Jews arriving grew, with many fleeing persecution in Europe. The murder of six million Jews during the Holocaust gave added urgency to demands for a safe haven. The Jewish population reached 630,000 just over 30% of the population, by 1947. In 1947, against a backdrop of growing violence between Jews and Arabs and against British rule the United Nations (UN) voted for Palestine to be split into separate Jewish and Arab states. Jerusalem would become an international city. No Arab nations supported this. Britain abstained. It decided to withdraw and to hand the problem to the UN at the end of 14 May 1948. Jewish leaders in Palestine declared an independent state known as Israel hours before British rule ended. The UN recognized Israel the following year.

What was the 1948 Arab-Israeli war?

Source: <https://mondediplo.com/maps/middleeast1948>

The day after Israel declared independence; it was attacked and surrounded by the armies of five Arab nations. The conflict came to be known in Israel as its war of independence. By the time the fighting ended with an armistice in 1949, Israel controlled most of the territory. Agreements left Egypt occupying the Gaza Strip, Jordan occupying the West Bank and East Jerusalem, and Israel occupying West Jerusalem. About 750,000 Palestinians fled, or were forced from, their homes on land which became Israel and ended up as refugees. The event is known in Arabic as the Nakba (Catastrophe). In the years that followed, hundreds of thousands of Jews left, or were expelled from, Muslim majority.

What was the 1967 Middle East war?

Source: https://cdn3.vox-cdn.com/assets/4239235/Israeli_territory_1949_to_1967.jpg

What is known as the Six-Day war changed boundaries in the Middle East and had major consequences for Palestinians. The war saw Israel fight Egypt, Syria and Jordan. It started when Israel, fearing an attack by Egypt and Syria, launched a strike on Egypt's air force. By the time the fighting ended, Israel had captured the Sinai Peninsula and Gaza from Egypt, most of the Golan Heights from Syria, and East Jerusalem

and the West Bank from Jordan. About a million Palestinians in the West Bank, Gaza and East Jerusalem came under Israel's control. Israel's occupation of the areas has lasted until this day. Israel signed a peace treaty with Egypt in 1979 and returned the Sinai. It annexed East Jerusalem and the Golan Heights, making them part of Israel.

What might Palestine and Gaza Strip look like?

The Gaza Strip is a stretch of land surrounded by Israel, Egypt and the Mediterranean Sea. It is 41 km (25 miles) long and 10km wide. Home to about 2.1 million people, it is one of the most densely populated places on Earth. Even before the latest war between Israel and Hamas, Gaza had one of the highest unemployment rates in the world. Many people were living below the poverty line and depending on food aid to survive. Gaza's boundaries were drawn up as a result of the 1948 Middle East war, when it was occupied by Egypt. Egypt was driven out of Gaza in the 1967 war and the Strip was occupied by Israel, which built settlements and placed Gaza's Palestinian population under military rule. In 2005, Israel unilaterally withdrew its troops and settlers from Gaza, though it retained control of its shared border, airspace and shoreline, giving it effective control of the movement of people and goods. The UN still regards Gaza as Israeli-occupied territory because of the level of control Israel has. Hamas won Palestinian elections in 2006, and ejected its rivals from territory after following year.

Israel and Egypt imposed a blockade in response, with Israel controlling most of what was allowed into the territory. In the years that followed, Hamas and Israel fought several major conflicts including those in 2008–09, 2012 and 2014. A major conflict between the two sides in May 2021 ended in a ceasefire after 11 days. On 07 October 2023, Hamas fighters launched an assault from Gaza, killing about, 1,200 people in Israel and taking 251 hostages. This triggered a massive Israeli military offensive, by land, sea and air. More than 61,000 people have been killed, according to the Hamas-run health ministry. In July, the UK and 27 other nations, including Australia, Canada, France, Italy, Japan, New Zealand and Switzerland called for an immediate end to the war. They said the suffering of civilians had “reached new depths”.

The same month, UN-backed experts warned the “worst-case scenario of famine is currently playing out” in the Gaza Strip. The Integrated Food Security Phase Classification (IPC) said there was mounting evidence that widespread starvation, malnutrition and disease were driving a rise in hunger related deaths. UN agencies had already warned of man-

made, mass starvation in Gaza. They have blamed the crisis on Israel, which controls the entry of all supplies to the territory. Israel has insisted that there are no restrictions on aid deliveries and that there is “no starvation”.

Sources: <https://herald.caoun.net/news/articlePrint.html?idno=18291>, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Gaza-Strip>

Advocates of the two-state solution have envisaged a Palestine in the Gaza strip and West Bank linked by a corridor through Israel. Two decades ago, details of how it might work were set out in a blueprint by former Israeli and Palestinian negotiators. Known as the Geneva Accord, its principles include recognition of Jerusalem’s Jewish neighborhoods as the Israel capital, and recognition of its Arab neighborhoods as the Palestinian capital, and a demilitarized Palestinian state. Israel would annex big settlements and cede other land in a swap, and resettle Jewish settlers in Palestinian sovereign territory outside there.

Is a two-state solution possible?

Obstacles have grown with time. While Israel withdrew settlers and soldiers from Gaza in 2005, settlements expanded in the West Bank and East Jerusalem, their population rising from 250,000 in 1993 to 695,000 three decades later, according to Israeli organization peace now. Palestinians say this undermines the basis of a viable state. During the second intifada, Israel also constructed what it described as a barrier to stop Palestinian attacks. Palestinians call it a land grab. The PA led by President Mahmoud Abbas administers islands of West Bank land enveloped by a zone of Israeli control comprising 60 of the territory, including the Jordanian border and the stalemates-arrangements set out the Oslo Accords.

What is the status of the West Bank now?

Source: <https://www.britannica.com/place/West-Bank>

The West Bank land between Israel and the River Jordan is home to an estimated three million Palestinians. Along with East Jerusalem and Gaza, it is part of what are widely known as the Occupied Palestinian Territories. The Palestinians have always opposed Israel's presence in these areas and want them to be part of a future independent state, something backed by the vast majority of the international community. Israel still has overall control of the West Bank, but since the 1990s, a Palestinian government—known as the Palestinian Authority has run most of its towns and cities. There are about 160 Israeli settlements, housing about 700,000 Jews, in the West Bank and East Jerusalem.

However, Israel's government disputes this. It says the biggest settlements at the very least are permanent and that all settlements are rooted in its historical rights. It does not recognize the right of the Palestinians to have their own state and argues that the West Bank is part of the Israeli homeland. The Israeli government announced plans to expand settlements after coming to power in 2022. It says the creation of a Palestinian state would be a threat to Israeli security. In July 2024, the top court of the UN, the International Court of Justice (ICJ), said that Israel's continued presence in the Occupied Palestinian Territories is illegal. It said that Israel should withdraw all settlers and that it was in breach of international agreement on racism and apartheid. There has been a sharp escalation in attacks by settlers against Palestinian villages since the 07 October 2023 Hamas attack on Israel. According to a report by the UN Office for Humanitarian Affairs, there were, 2,208 attacks by settlers against Palestinians resulting in casualties or property damage between January 2024 and June 2025.

Two-States theory solution:

Has a deal ever been close? the two-state solution was the bedrock

of the U.S.-backed peace process ushered in by the 1993 Oslo Accords, signed by Yasser Arafat of the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) and Israeli Prime Minister Yitzhak Rabin. The accords led the PLO to recognize Israel's right to exist and renounce violence and to the creation of the Palestinian Authority (PA). Palestinians hoped this would be a step towards an independent state, with East Jerusalem as the capital. The process was hit by rejection on both sides. In 2000, U.S. President Bill Clinton brought Arafat and Israeli Prime Minister Ehud Barak to Camp David to clinch a deal, but the effort failed. The fate of Jerusalem, deemed by Israel as its "eternal and indivisible" capital, was the main obstacle. The conflict escalated with a second Palestinian intifada (uprising) in 2000–2005. U.S. administrations sought to revive peacemaking to no avail, with the last bid collapsing in 2014.

According to Antonio Guterres, The UN Secretary General said that, "It is long past time to move in a determined, irreversible way toward a two-state solution, on the basis of United Nations resolutions and international law, with Israel and Palestine living side-by-side in peace, and security, with Jerusalem as the capital of both state". The "two-state solution" is an internationally backed formula for peace between Israel and the Palestinians. It proposes an independent Palestinian state in the West Bank and Gaza, with East Jerusalem as its capital. It would exist alongside Israel. Israel rejects a two-state solution. It says any final settlement must be the result of negotiations with the Palestinians with the Palestinians, and statehood should not be a precondition. The Palestinian Authority backs a two-state solution but Hamas does not because it is opposed to the existence of Israel. Hamas says that it could accept an interim Palestinian state based on 1967 de facto borders, without officially recognizing Israel, if refugees were given the right to return. Earlier efforts to settle the conflict saw Israel and Palestinian leaders sign a deal called the Oslo Peace Accords, in 1993. This was intended to provide a framework for peace talks. However, collapsed with each side blaming the other.

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